

MEMORANDUM

THE JUBILEE HOUSE(THE COMMITTEE ON CONSTITUTIONAL AND
LEGAL AFFAIRS)

ACCRA – GHANA

23rd SEPTEMBER,2021.

INFORMATION

TO : THE COMMITTEE ON CONSTITUTIONAL AFFAIRS

FROM : B [REDACTED] O [REDACTED] -T [REDACTED] G [REDACTED]

SUBJECT: KILL THE ANTI-LGBTQIA BILL

In the interest of promoting a peaceful and harmonious coexisting human relationship between people of sexual majority(heterosexual) and minority sexual orientation in Ghana, we (LGBTQIA), being the under cared and uncover for members under Laws of this country, have committed today to improve upon the right and freedom that have been denied us for years as a deserving members of our beloved country. This solemn procession agreement, which has stirred unwanted controversy and hatred towards my community (LGBTQAI) across the country due to the whether minority sexuality should be legalized or illegalized. In Chapter Five (5) Article 12, claus 2 of the constitution referred to the respect of the fundamental human rights of each and every individual in the country and I would like to put emphasis on the word human. Human is a being who is genderless, can be male or female, trans-male or a trans-female, can be heterosexual or gay, can be bisexual or transsexual and so on. With such understanding the question I lie before us all is to why we think LGBTQIA should be denied their rights? Whiles the constitution of our beloved country says otherwise. I believe Ghana is made up of people from different walk of life be a Traditionalist, Christian, Muslim, Buddhist, Spiritualist or unbeliever of the above mentioned and others. So why the constitution with a test of time be enforced to favor a certain group of people in the country leaving other minority with their own fate, be it women abuse, child abuse or gay men abuse, the LGBTQIA, has been reached freely with abuse and discrimination from time to time in broad day light for hundreds of years in this country and today we are in good faith demanding for what has being denied us for the longest of time, we demand equal rights and demand that the dehumanization of LGBTQIA should stop and we should be given respect , and I commits these honorable house and committee responsible for

enforcing the laws to respect and adhere to certain key principles, and to follow up the principles of the law with a number of concrete steps and actions to stop the harassment and discrimination against the LGBTQIA Community.

We say kill the anti-LGBTQIA bill because this anti-LGBTQIA legislation, on the side of LGBTQIA Community will promote injustice, maltreatment, ,discrimination and hatred towards our current and future generations in Ghana. It is for the good of our mental, physical, social and economical right covers that we seek to be also protected and act upon our right for a better life conditions as citizens of the country, on the side of the committee, the president and other officials who haven't signed this legislation should give it a thought over to kill it, and to the current and future affiliates of the bill at the enterprise level we hope you have a chance to come to agreement with us to see reason with us because a proper solution can be alternated rather than a harsh legislation just to erase people of their rights imagining your own flesh and blood befallen to these laws you thought harsh to establish. Any registered union or organizations and individuals should "opt-in" to support the LGBTQIA community by informing and reporting in writing or oral to institutions responsible for enforcing and making sure human right is not abused or stood upon, I will urge institutions like Ministry of gender, children and social protection and NGOs that focus on such issues should help us to stop segregation of the Anti-LGBTQIA. As the constitution of Ghana states the right of all citizens should be protected. If the bill is kill and the LGBTQIA is signed shall promote and encourage the spirit of together and tolerance for each other's community and the role one plays in its own. The LGBTQIA community have all employers and workers of different professions and the thought of religious community trying to tear up our community with outrageous actions concerning how they view us from(wanting us to be the villains to their story which we aren't). The society as whole have always been the tantrums encouraging fellow people to hate on us, encourage people to take delight in torturing people with minority community be it difference of their sexuality, schools allowing fellow students to dehumanize other students because of their sexuality, families disowning their children and relatives because of the stigma of being gay, lesbian, bisexual and so on. We continue to suffer violence from people just by our mere existence and other forms of abuse due to our differences with others, since we are all citizens of this country we ask for our rights to be free from this oppression from the arbitrators

aggressive straight people who now sought for the imprisonment of people of my community. We hope to get our rights revived so we can live in freedom and peace. I hope the monitoring mechanism agreed to institute laws not to only normalize people like us but to also make laws to protect and help us. The way forward for our peaceful existence relationship from both parts is for either party finds a way learning to tolerate and allow each other the benefit of the doubt of demonizing ourselves based on fractures ignorant knowledge of society, through the monitoring mechanism I hope our voices are heard as I believe we live in a democratic society of the 21st century. We say kill the bill, so that violations and criminalization against my fellow LGBTQIA or other minorities be stop. You can't agree to my lifestyle but my life is something that shouldn't be agreed upon because it's my birth right and a natural right is untradeable. We may choose to declare the Anti-LGBTQIA null and void, However, it shouldn't be the matter of may or may not because its humanity we are talking about and there we deserves our rights and legitimacy to live in whatsoever sexuality we are. Minority rights activist like us can participate in the process by choice but along with all we must respect the authority and we have no right to initiate or disrupt bargaining to the decision you take but we hope to be recognized and appreciated for who we truly are over the negative outrage thought of the straight people of us. I hope that this debate will be settled in accordance with a thoroughly comprehensive dispute procedure with binding arbitration on rights disputes. No strike of deceptive power should the government officials take to influence the decision over disputes of rights. My fellow LGBTQIA and I believe in the course of the laws and trust that our life right will be dimmed fit to be institute in the constitution of our homeland. We the LGBTQIA have agree to follow the dispute resolution procedures and not resort to violent during the process of decision making. We pray and believe the will of God will take it's course.

I hope this summary will prove helpful in meeting your needs in rethinking about establishing of our right. I hope this will be a call to action on this matter.